

Optimisation of CT scanning for characterisation of carbon fibre pressure vessel microstructure

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KU LEUVEN

MATERIALS ENGINEERING

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Composite pressure vessels

How are they made and what defects can they have?

Filament winding of composite pressure vessels

Fibre Spools

Winding tension control

Comb

Alignment control

Resin bath

Impregnation rate control

Nip rollers

Winding angle control

Rotating liner/
Mandrel

Low control of processing parameters

Microstructural variability /defects

Effect of variability on performance
Optimised design

Microstructural variabilities and defects

Which parameters are of interest and why?

Voids

- Affect thermo-mechanical performance
- Act as crack initiation sites

Fibre misalignment

- Reduces tensile modulus
- Reduces load-carrying capacity

Fibre volume fraction variation

- Affects local and global strength
- Affects stress recovery length

Microstructural variabilities and defects

Which parameters are of interest and why?

Voids

Fibre misalignment

Fibre volume fraction variation

All variabilities/defects are affected by manufacturing parameters

Voids

- Affect thermo-mechanical performance
- Act as crack initiation sites

- Reduces tensile modulus
- Reduces load-carrying capacity

- Affects local and global strength
- Affects stress recovery length

Microstructural variabilities in filament winding

Voids

Fibre misalignment

Fibre volume fraction variation

* Most studies focus on hoop layers given their contribution to burst performance

Microstructural variabilities in filament winding

Voids

Fibre misalignment

Fibre volume fraction variation

Layer
compaction

High void fraction, complex shape

A micrograph showing a complex, irregular pattern of voids (dark spots) within a matrix, indicating high void fraction and complex shapes.

Accurate and representative microstructural characterisation is vital!
Optimum characterisation strategy needs to be defined

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A micrograph showing a pattern of fibers that are not perfectly aligned, illustrating fibre misalignment.

* Most studies focus on hoop layers given their contribution to burst performance

Micro-CT for pressure vessel characterisation

Methodology, scan parameters and challenges

Micro-CT scan and preliminary observations

Micro-CT scan –
Tescan UniTom HR

Qualitative observations - 1

Qualitative observations - 2

- What **voxel sizes** should be used to capture all variabilities and defects?
- What **scan parameters** should be used for optimising **quality** and **time**?
- Which locations and **how many samples** should be scanned for a **representative analysis**?

How can we get representative microstructure?

Representative microstructural analysis =

Optimum scanning parameters + Optimum segmentation strategy
(scale vs. time)

x

statistically representative samples
(location of sample, number of samples)

Scan parameter optimisation

Voxel size(s) and scanning modes

Void and fibre visualisation

Voids (big, complex) → low resolution

Fibre related variabilities → high resolution

Voxel size(s) and scanning modes

Focus mode

For lower resolution (voids)

Scan time optimisation with sufficient image quality

1.6 μm with binning in microfocus mode

Voxel size modification based on observations

- \uparrow Voxel size \rightarrow \uparrow scanned volume \rightarrow more representative analysis
- Void size distribution for 11 pressure vessels
- Small voids ($< 10000 \mu\text{m}^3$) contribute less than 10% to overall void content
 - voxel size increased to 2 or 2.5 μm with binning

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Fibre visualisation

Void visualisation

Segmentation

Voids

Fibre misalignment

Fibre volume fraction
(local)

Deep-learning segmentation

Local (fibre tracking)

Smart selection of scan locations

Representative analysis

Representative analysis

Circumferential position analysis

To determine number of samples to be scanned at the axial location

Method:

Circumferential position analysis

Distribution fitting

Following fits were tested:

Normal

Lognormal

Weibull

Gamma

Generalised extreme value

Number of samples based on distributions:

Within 10% of mean - Estimated $N \sim 15/16$

Within 20% of mean - Estimated $N \sim 8$

Circumferential position analysis

Spatial correlation

Spatial correlation computed using Contiguity matrix (weighting of neighbors) and Moran's I (MI)

No spatial correlation found

With consideration of immediate neighbors only → weak negative correlation

With consideration of weighted contribution from all neighbors → perfect randomness

Significance of autocorrelation → p-value not significant

MI = -1 : Perfect dispersion
(Clustering of dissimilar values)

MI = 0: Perfect randomness

MI = 1 : Perfect clustering
(Clustering of similar values)

Circumferential position analysis

Cumulative mean analysis - method

Methodology:

Mean with increasing number of samples

Observe when trend becomes stable → ideal # of samples

N-side polygon with selected origin
up to N = 19

Circumferential position analysis

Cumulative mean analysis - results

Analysis with each location as origin

N = 4+ samples, well distributed

Axial position analysis

Failure observed mostly near centre of the pressure vessel

Simulation and literature → approximate zone of failure

Further microstructure analysis for the below highlighted zone in progress

Conclusions

Optimised and **representative** microstructure analysis for composite pressure vessels

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